

**IMPROVING THE IDENTIFICATION AND ASSESSMENT OF THE TAX
POTENTIAL OF THE REGIONS
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ВЫЯВЛЕНИЯ И ОЦЕНКИ НАЛОГОВОГО
ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕГИОНОВ**

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Annotation: Due to the fact that the tax potential determines future tax revenues to budgets of all levels, the assessment of its value provides for the development of strategic directions of the tax policy of the region by optimizing the fiduciary burden of Real income planning.

Аннотация: В связи с тем, что налоговый потенциал определяет будущие налоговые поступления в бюджеты всех уровней, оценка его величины предусматривает разработку стратегических направлений налоговой политики региона путем оптимизации фидуциарной нагрузки планирования реальных доходов.

Key words: tax revenues, fiscal policy, tax burden, potential, region

Ключевые слова: налоговые поступления, налогово-бюджетная политика, налоговая нагрузка, потенциал, регион

Since the tax potential determines the future tax revenues for budgets of all levels, the assessment of its value ensures the Real planning of revenues, the optimization of the tax burden and the development of strategic directions of the tax policy of the region.

The effectiveness of these measures implies an integrated approach to the management of the tax potential of the territory, this is T.No, it's not. Reflected in the model developed by Tkacheva. In his opinion, the guiding principles of the country's development and the goals of the tax reform being implemented, as well as the problems arising in the implementation of modern fiscal policy, necessitate the development and implementation of a model of tax capacity building, which includes three main directions (Table 3).

Table 3

Investment capacity building model of the region¹

<p>Objective-development of the tax potential of the territory</p>	<p>Improving tax conditions for doing business</p>	<p>1. Legal direction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop a budget strategy for the territory, based on tax directions.
		<p>2. Institutional orientation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - development of competitive advantages of regional administrative centers; - increase collection of tax and non-tax receipts; - to identify the types of economic activities that are promising for regional development.

¹ U.A.Yuldasheva Monograph "Improving the methodology for determining and analyzing the tax potential of regions". TMI 2022.

		<p>3. Information direction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - information systems of fiscal relations; - to ensure openness and transparency of public finances.
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According to the table, the model of increasing the investment potential of the territory is indicated, the main purpose of which is to develop the tax potential of the territory. The legal direction, institutional direction and information directions and their components for creating tax conditions for doing business are mentioned.

The mixed approach combines the main aspects of the characteristics of the resource and fiscal approaches. In this case, the concept of tax potential is understood as the maximum amount of income that can be collected to the state budget from tax at the expense of resources in these regions for a certain period of time.

The only methodology for calculating the tax potential of the Territory has not yet been developed. To calculate this, it is proposed, in particular, to estimate the revenues of the budget system as a ratio between the internal territorial product.

But, as we think, the calculation in this method is not an object, and most importantly, it cannot immediately reflect the real situation on the territory.

The problem lies in the fact that when calculating the gross regional product, it is repeatedly corrected by the statistics of territorial authorities, which does not allow for a quick analysis and assessment of the tax potential of the territory.

Based on a representative tax system, the assessment of the tax potential of the territory is divided into several methods that differ from each other in their approach to assessing the tax base in the territory.

Among these, it is necessary to highlight the regulatory and expanded approaches.

The first one is based on the probability of receiving information from the tax authorities to calculate all taxes in the territory and indicators of the tax base falling on the territory's budget. Indirect methods are used when it is not possible to use direct methods when assessing tax potential.

Thus, on the principles of self-sufficiency at the territorial level, the quantitative determination of the financial conditions for its development is ensured. In our opinion, the methods of assessing the tax potential can be conditionally combined into four groups² (Table 4):

Table 4

Methods of tax capacity assessment³

Method	Advantages of the method	Disadvantages of the method
1. Methods of valuation using economic income indicators		
Average per capita income of the population	Reflect not only the regional budget funds, but also the revenues from the Republican budget. There is a database for calculations	It does not allow to take into account the insignificant incomes of local budgets
Assessment on the basis of gross regional product	Takes into account the income of residents and non-residents	The volume of GDP does not take into account the inequality

² “[Tax Reform of 2019 in Uzbekistan*](#)” 2020/10/24. YU Asanaliyevna - International Journal on Integrated Education

³ U.A.Yuldasheva Monograph "Improving the methodology for determining and analyzing the tax potential of regions". TMI 2022.

		of the bases (composition of production) and tax rates in different regions
Method of total taxable resources	More accurate image actual size tax resources	Large amount statistical indicator information base
2. Methods of evaluation based on the construction of a tax performance representation system		
Tax representation system	It can be used to determine the tax potential, taking into account the actual capabilities and the current practice of forming tax bases	High working capacity
Correlation-regression analysis method	Low labor intensity, noticeable objectivity. Allows to determine the relevance of real receipts and tax bases to factors	The choice of indicators for calculation is ambiguous, complicating its application at the territorial level
3. Methods of assessment based on the data of the tax report forms and corrections to the actual collected amount of taxes		

Calculation based on the additional property of the tax capacity	The difference in the calculation of types of taxes allows us to achieve a fairly accurate result. Determining the speed of collection increases the reliability of the information received	The information base is the data of the retrospective period, the current and future status of the tax base is not taken into account.
Simplified method	Availability of reference, ease of Assembly	Difficult to calculate due to insufficient parameters
Planned method	High level of accuracy	Limited calculations due to the fact that the parameters are used less
Method of assessment based on the correction of the amount of fees collected in practice in the territory in the base year	Convenience of data collection, their availability	Low reliability of results
4. Method of valuation using the tax Potential Index (TPI)		
Evaluation using TPI	High level of confidence	Huge amount of historical data required

This table presents the methods for assessing tax potential. According to him, we divided the methods into four groups and showed the advantages and disadvantages of the method.

The study of the existing methods of assessing the tax potential was based on the fact that none of them were considered standard and mandatory, which indicates the need to use combined approaches, as well as develop directions for their improvement. At the same time, it is desirable to optimize the list of general economic parameters, the choice of which is determined by the goals, time limits and specific types of tax at a certain stage of the calculation of taxes. It should be noted that the data used to assess the tax potential of the territory should meet the following requirements:⁴:

- accuracy and reliability;
- taking into account the maximum number of factors affecting the financial position of the territory;
- versatility

The analysis of the problem of finding the optimal method of assessing the tax potential of the subject that makes up the country, allowed to confirm the fact that it is necessary to carry out it by collecting the results obtained by each type of tax.

The conducted research gave grounds to the fact that when assessing the tax potential, it is necessary to take into account not only the characteristics of the tax base, but also the debt to the budget system for each type of tax, as well as the payment of part of the debt in previous years. The algorithm for assessing the potential value of the tax is the implementation of the following procedures in a row⁵:

⁴ T. Teshabaev, Sh. Allayarov, U. Yuldasheva “Indicators of Tax Potential of Regions in Financial Security and Its Determining Factors”. International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding ISSN 2364-5369 Volume 8, Issue 12 December, 2021 Pages: 243-248

⁵ Sagdillayeva Z. Yuldasheva U. (2020)“Theoretical aspects of the tax potential of the state's regions” ACADEMICIA an International Multidisciplinary research journal Vol.10 Issue 3

1. An assessment of the share of taxes in the overall composition of receipts during the year as a percentage;
2. An assessment of the debt as a percentage on each of the taxes;
3. Calculation of the capacity to fulfill tax obligations on taxes;
4. Calculation of the total capacity for the performance of tax obligations during the year;
5. Determination of the total tax potential of the territory.

This takes into account not only the specifics of the tax base, but also the debt to the budget for each tax.

In the process of summarizing the results of research and analysis conducted by several scientists, the following main reasons for the decline in the coefficient of capacity, budget revenues were identified:

1. Reduce the collection of taxes per capita, taking into account the standard of living. This is the most important criterion that most often characterizes the position of the territory in the tax sphere. Its importance is the greatest, since it distinguishes territories as "poor" and "rich", determines the overall level of development of the territory and the current state of its economy (respectively, the level of tax potential of the territory).
2. Instability of tax collection, that is, the level of tax collection varies from year to year. The greater the difference in tax collection, the more stable the overall economic development of a particular territory will be (that is, the tax potential of the territory is unstable).
3. Borrowing for tax collection indicates the level of indebtedness of economic entities. To some extent, this indicator characterizes the financial situation of the main taxpayers of the Territory.

4. Changes in tax policy to ensure compliance with tax legislation.

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